

To assess the effectiveness of teaching program on knowledge and practices regarding of metabolic syndrome Among senior citizen

Miss varsha kunjir¹, DR. Sonopant Joshi²

¹Second Year MSc Nursing; Symbiosis College of Nursing, Symbiosis International (Deemed University), SIU, Pune.

²Director of Symbiosis college of Nursing, Symbiosis International (Deemed University), SIU, Pune.

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Abstract

Metabolic syndrome is a grouping of cardiac risk factors that result from insulin resistance. Early diagnosis is important in order to employ lifestyle and risk factor modification. To assess the effectiveness of teaching program on knowledge and practice related to metabolic syndrome. In that non-experimental method used. And using non-probability convenience sampling technique, 60 sample were selected in this study. In that 18.3% of them had moderate knowledge (score 7-13) and 81.7% of them had good knowledge (score 14-20). in pretest was 8.3 which increased to 15.9 in posttest. T-value for this test was 16.3 with 59 degrees of freedom. Hence teaching program is effective. in practice Average practice score in pretest was 65.5. which increased to 83.9 in posttest-value for this test was 22.8 with 59 degrees of freedom. calculated 't' value is more than tabulated value and calculated 'p' value was less than accepted level of P=0.05 There was a statistically significant difference between the means of the pre-test and post test scores of practices among senior citizen. **Conclusion:** The study showed that the planned teaching on knowledge and practice of metabolic syndrome among senior citizen was effective in improving the knowledge and practice thus helps them to understand the meaning.

Keywords: *Metabolic syndrome, knowledge, effectiveness and planned teaching.*

Introduction: Metabolic syndrome (Met's) is a widely prevalent and multi-factorial disorder. The syndrome has been given several names such as insulin resistance (IR) syndrome, paurometabolism syndrome, Reaven's syndrome, Syndrome X, and the deadly quartet. ((Abhishek Gupta et al 2010) The insulin resistance/metabolic syndrome is characterized by the variable co-existence of hyperinsulinemia, obesity, dyslipidemia (small dense low-density lipoprotein, hypertriglyceridemia, and decreased high-density lipoprotein cholesterol), and hypertension. The pathogenesis of the syndrome has multiple origins. However, obesity and sedentary lifestyle coupled with diet and still largely unknown genetic factors clearly interact to produce the syndrome. (Genovefa D. Kolovou 2007) MetSyn prevalence is present in approximately 25% of all adults with increased prevalence in advanced ages. The presence of one component of MetSyn increases the risk of developing MetSyn later in life and likely represents a high lifetime burden of cardiovascular disease risk. (Paul B. Nolan et al 2017). The effect of extreme obesity on mortality is greater among younger than older adults. In this respect, obesity is also associated with increased risk of several cancer types. (Atila Engin et al 2017) India is a major contributor to the global cardiovascular mortality and there is increasing trends in prevalence of various components of the metabolic syndrome (Rajeev Gupta 2004) During 2007–2014, the age-adjusted weighted prevalence (\pm standard error) of Met's among U.S. adults was $34.3 \pm 0.8\%$. In age-stratified analysis, $54.9 \pm 1.7\%$ of elderly population aged 60 and over had Met's. (Doosup Shin et al 2018) The metabolic syndrome is a high-risk state for diabetes and cardiovascular disease. Little is known about its prevalence and prevention in those with impaired glucose tolerance.(Trevor J. Orchard, 2019) Older adults with diabetes experience greater barriers to practicing self-care activities necessary for disease control than their younger counterparts. It was hypothesized that post educational follow-up intervention would increase self-care knowledge scores, improve metabolic control, and reduce self-care behavioral deficits.(Kuei-Shen Tu et al 1993,) Randomized controlled trials have shown that exercise training has a mild or moderate favorable effect on many metabolic and cardiovascular risk factors that constitute or are related to the metabolic syndrome (MetS). (Timo A. Lakka et al 2007)

Hypothesis:

H0- There is no significant changes in knowledge and practice regarding of metabolic syndrome among senior citizen after administration of teaching program.

H1: There will be significant difference between the level of practice regarding metabolic syndrome among senior citizen after posttest.

H2: There will be a significant association between the practice regarding metabolic syndrome among senior citizen with their selected demographic variables.

- Senior citizen group need to maintain good practices. teaching program is 1 hr. daily for 3 days

Table no:1 Table showing the Activity planning of teaching programme.

SRNO.	ACTIVITY OF TEACHING PROGRAM	TIME
1.	EXERCISE	1HR
2.	DIET	1HR
3.	LIFESTYLE CHANGES	1HR

Analytic strategies:

The improvement of good practice score in posttest were used to measure the outcome. The paired t test, chi square test, mean, and standard deviation were used to analyze the data.

Ethical Consideration:

The research was approved by the institutional research committee (Proposal No. SIU/IEC/572), and the concerned senior citizen group authorities granted permission to collect the sample for the study. The study's goal and methodology were adequately explained to the participants before they signed a written informed consent form. Sample privacy was maintained.

Analysis of Demographic variables.**Table 2. Description of samples (senior citizens) based on their personal characteristics.**

(N=60)

Demographic variable	Frequency	%
Age		
60-65 years	19	31.7%
65-70 years	17	28.3%
70-75 years	18	30.0%
75-above	6	10.0%
Gender		
Male	32	53.3%
Female	28	46.7%
Height		
110 to 120 cm	12	20.0%
130 to 140 cm	19	31.7%
140 to 150 cm	18	30.0%
150 cm and above	11	18.3%
Weight		
50 to 60 kg	11	18.3%
60 to 70 kg	16	26.7%
80 to 90 kg	17	28.3%
90 and above	16	26.7%
BMI		
15 to 18	10	16.7%
18 to 24	17	28.3%
25 to 29	18	30.0%
30 to 35	15	25.0%
Are u suffering from?		
Diabetes mellitus	32	53.3%
Hypertension	28	46.7%

In this study, 6 demographic variables were taken into consideration. Table 1 presents the population's frequency according to their personal characteristics. 31.7% of the senior citizens had age 60-65 years, 28.3% of them had age 65-70 years, 30% of them had age 70-75 years and 10% of them had age above 75 years. 53.3% of them were males and 46.7% of them were females. 20% of them had height 110 to 120 cm, 31.7% of them had height 130 to 140 cm, 30% of them had height 140 to 150 cm and 18.3% of them had height above 150 cm. 18.3% of them had weight 50 to 60 kg, 26.7% of them had weight 60 to 70 kg, 28.3% of them had weight 80 to 90 kg and 26.7% of them had weight above 90 kg. 16.7% of them had BMI 15 to 18, 28.3% of them had BMI 18 to 24, 30% of them had BMI 25 to 29 and 25% of them had BMI 30 to 35. 53.3% of them were suffering from diabetes mellitus and 46.7% of them had hypertension.

Table 3: Knowledge regarding of metabolic syndrome after intervention

N=60

Knowledge	Pretest		Posttest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Poor	23	38.3%	0	0.0%
Moderate	35	58.3%	11	18.3%
Good	2	3.3%	49	81.7%

In pretest, 38.3% of the senior citizens had poor knowledge (score 0-6), 58.3% of them had moderate knowledge (score 7-13) and 3.3% of them had good knowledge (score 14-20) regarding prevention of complication of metabolic syndrome. In posttest 18.3% of them had moderate knowledge (score 7-13) and 81.7% of them had good knowledge (score 14-20) regarding prevention of complication of metabolic syndrome. This indicates that the knowledge among senior citizens regarding prevention of complication of metabolic syndrome improved remarkably after teaching program.

Table 4: Practices regarding of metabolic syndrome after intervention.

Practices	Pretest		Posttest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Poor	0	0.0%		0.0%
Average	13	21.7%	0	0.0%
Good	47	78.3%	8	13.3%
Excellent	0	0.0%	52	86.7%

In pretest, 21.7% of the senior citizens had average practices (score 41-60) and 78.3% of them had good practices (Score 61-80) regarding prevention of complication of metabolic syndrome. In posttest, 13.3% of the senior citizens had good practices (score 61-80) and 86.7% of them had good practices (score 81-100) regarding prevention of complication of metabolic syndrome. This indicates that the practices among senior citizens regarding prevention of complication of metabolic syndrome improved remarkably after teaching program.

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of teaching program on knowledge and practices regarding of metabolic syndrome.

Table 5: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of teaching program on knowledge regarding of metabolic syndrome

N=60

	Mean	S D	T	def.	p-value
Pretest	8.3	3.1	16.3	59	0.000
Posttest	15.9	2.5			

searcher applied paired t-test for the effectiveness of teaching program knowledge regarding prevention of complication of metabolic syndrome. Average knowledge score in pretest was 8.3 which increased to 15.9 in posttest. T-value for this test was 16.3 with 59 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. It is evident that the teaching program is significantly effective

in improving the knowledge among senior citizens regarding prevention of complication of metabolic syndrome

Table 6: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of teaching program on practices regarding of metabolic syndrome

N=60

	Mean	S D	T	df	p-value
Pretest	65.5	4.9	22.8	59	0.000
Posttest	83.9	3.5			

Researcher applied paired t-test for the effectiveness of teaching program practices regarding prevention of complication of metabolic syndrome. Average practice score in pretest was 65.5 which increased to 83.9 in posttest. T-value for this test was 22.8 with 59 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. It is evident that the teaching program is significantly effective in improving the practices among senior citizens regarding prevention of complication of metabolic syndrome

Table 7: Analysis of data related to association of knowledge and practices with selected demographic variable N=60

Demographic variable Knowledge

		Poor	Moderate	Good	p-value
Age	60-65 years	9	9	1	0.759
	65-70 years	7	10	0	
	70-75 years	6	11	1	
	75-above	1	5	0	
Gender	Male	12	19	1	1.000
	Female	11	16	1	
Height	110 to 120 cm	4	8	0	0.195
	130 to 140 cm	9	9	1	
	140 to 150 cm	4	14	0	
	150 cm and above	6	4	1	
Weight	50 to 60 kg	1	10	0	0.087
	60 to 70 kg	8	8	0	
	80 to 90 kg	6	9	2	
	90 and above	8	8	0	
BMI	15 to 18	5	5	0	0.573
	18 to 24	7	8	2	
	25 to 29	6	12	0	
	30 to 35	5	10	0	
Are you suffering from?	Diabetes mellitus	14	18	0	0.263
	Hypertension	9	17	2	

Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variable was found to have significant association with the knowledge among senior citizens regarding of metabolic syndrome.

Table 8: Fisher's exact test for the association of practices with demographic variable

Demographi variable		Practices		p- value
		Average	Good	
Age	60-65 years	6	13	0.597
	65-70 years	2	15	
	70-75 years	4	14	
	75-above	1	5	
Gender	Male	5	27	0.347
	Female	8	20	
Height	110 to 120 cm	1	11	0.656
	130 to 140 cm	5	14	
	140 to 150 cm	5	13	
	150 cm andabove	2	9	
Weight	50 to 60 kg	4	7	0.707
	60 to 70 kg	3	13	
	80 to 90 kg	3	14	
	90 and above	3	13	
BMI	15 to 18	3	7	0.095
	18 to 24	2	15	
	25 to 29	7	11	
	30 to 35	1	14	
Are you suffering from?	Diabete s mellitus	4	28	0.115
	Hypertension	9	19	

Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variable was found to have significant association with the practices among senior citizens regarding of metabolic syndrome.

Discussion

In this study it is indicated that post test show that In that 18.3% of them had moderate knowledge (score 7-13) and 81.7% of them had good knowledge (score 14-20). in pretest was 8.3 which increased to 15.9 in posttest. T-value for this test was 16.3 with 59 degrees of freedom. Average practice score in pretest was 65.5. which increased to 83.9 in posttest-value for this test was 22.8 with 59 degrees of freedom. Hence teaching program is effective. Hence it is statistically interpreted that planned teaching on knowledge regarding knowledge and practice of metabolic syndrome was effective. There is significant association of knowledge and practice score associated with senior citizen.. The results showed a significant inverse trend between whole-grain intake and the metabolic syndrome (P for trend = 0.005) and mortality from cardiovascular disease (P for trend = 0.04), independent of demographic, lifestyle, and dietary factors. Fasting glucose concentrations and body mass index decreased across increasing quartile categories of whole-grain intake (P for trend = 0.01 and 0.03, respectively), independent of confounders, whereas intake of refined grain was positively associated with higher fasting glucose concentrations (P for trend = 0.04) and a higher prevalence of the metabolic syndrome (P for trend = 0.01). (Sahyoun Nadine R et al 2006)

The knowledge effects ranged from 0.49 to 1.05; self-care behavior effects from 0.17 to 0.57, with insulin injection and weight loss associated with the smallest effect sizes; metabolic control from 0.16 to 0.41; and psychological outcomes 0.27. Mean age of the subjects was negatively correlated with knowledge and cholesterol, indicating that the older the mean age of the subjects, the lower the effects of patient education on these variables. (Sharon A. Brown 1990)

At baseline 19.5% of the men had MetS. The ORs of the metabolic syndrome at baseline were 4.7 (95% CI 4.2–5.3) in overweight and 30.6 (26.7–35.0) in obese men compared with normal weight men. A total of 477 deaths (160 CVD) occurred in 10.2 years of follow-up. The risks of all-cause mortality were 1.11 (0.75–1.17) in normal weight, 1.09 (0.82–1.47) in overweight, and 1.55 (1.14–2.11) in obese men with MetS compared with normal weight healthy men. The

corresponding risks for CVD mortality were 2.06 (0.92–4.63) in normal weight, 1.80 (1.10–2.97) in overweight, and 2.83 (1.70–4.72) in obese men with the MetS compared with normal weight healthy men. (Peter T. Katzmarzyk, 2005)

A total of 402 patients with hypertension and 114 patients with diabetes were enrolled. Mean (\pm SD) knowledge scores for patients with hypertension with inadequate (n=189), marginal (n=49), or adequate (n=155) literacy were 13.2 ± 3.1 , 15.3 ± 2.2 , and 16.5 ± 2.3 , respectively (range, 4-20; $P<.001$). A total of 92% of patients with hypertension and adequate literacy levels knew that a blood pressure reading of 160/100 mm Hg was high compared with 55% of those in the lowest reading level ($P<.001$)

(Mark V. Williams, 1998)

The study shows that 8(13.33%) had good level of knowledge score, 34(56.67%) have very good level of knowledge 18(30%) had excellent level of knowledge score. Hence planned teaching was effective, calculated 't' value is more than tabulated value and calculated 'p' value was less than accepted level of $P=0.05$ thus H_1 is statistically accepted. There is significant association of knowledge score associated with family history of hypertension and diabetic. (Meera R. Pohane1 2020) The Arabic Summary of Diabetes Self-care Activities (ASDSCA) instrument proved to have very acceptable psychometric properties: split half reliability test-retest (.912, $p = <.001$); and Cronbach's alpha . The internal consistency of the instrument's sub-scales was good for diet , exercise blood glucose testing , and foot care . Factor analysis revealed the presence of four components explaining 34.4%, 16%, 15.4%, and 11.2% of the variance of daily self-management practices for these items respectively (accumulated total of 77.1%).

(Aljohani, Khalid A.2011)

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the current study, it could be recommended that,

Future research should include a replication of this study using large sample size. Comparative study can be done on college teachers and school teachers.

Analogous study could be performed in different age group and in different professionals. Similar study can be conducted in terms of practice and attitude.

CONCLUSION:

The findings indicate that the of the study was conducted with the purpose to assess the effectiveness of teaching programmed on knowledge and.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION:

All authors met the criteria of the International Committee for Medical Journal Editors through direct contributions to the design and conduct of this study. All authors had significantly revised the draft and confirmed the final version of the manuscript.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Research data are not publicly shared because of privacy restrictions.

ETHICS APPROVAL STATEMENT

Ethical consideration is taken from the internal committee of the institute after approval from IRC No – SIU/IEC/574 The permission is taken from different senior citizen group in Pune to perform the study. The consent is taken by the participants before conducting the study and the permission letter for the conduction the study in different senior citizen group is also taken.

PATIENT CONSENT STATEMENT

After reading the documents explaining the study, all participants provided web-based informed consent.

PERMISSION TO REPRODUCE TO MATERIAL FROM OTHER SOURCES

Not applicable.

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